

Immobilization and Stabilization of an Engineered Acyltransferase for the Continuous Biosynthesis of Simvastatin in Packed-Bed Reactors

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6 **KEYWORDS:** biocatalysis, protein engineering, protein immobilization, continuous flow reactor,
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8 acyltransferase, simvastatin.
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12 **ABSTRACT** Simvastatin is a top-selling cholesterol-lowering drug traditionally obtained through
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14 a semi-synthetic process starting from lovastatin. However, this process is cost-demanding and
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16 makes use of chemical reagents that can generate considerable waste. The sustainability concerns
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18 underlying the current semi-synthetic process encouraged us to immobilize an engineered
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20 acyltransferase LovD-BuCh2 on different porous carriers to develop an innovative and sustainable
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22 process for the continuous biomanufacturing of simvastatin. We systematically assessed the effect
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24 of the immobilization on the functional and structural properties of the immobilized enzyme, the
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26 enzyme spatial distribution across the solid material, and the thermal stability of the immobilized
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28 biocatalysts. After screening several immobilization carriers, we selected LovD-BuCh2
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30 immobilized on the controlled porous glass particles functionalized with Fe³⁺-catechol complexes
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32 (EziG1) as the most suitable heterogeneous biocatalyst to optimize the continuous synthesis of
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34 simvastatin. This immobilized enzyme was four times more thermally stable than its free
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36 counterpart and maintained > 60% product yield during 5 operational cycles in batch. Under the
37
38 optimal flow conditions, we achieved 100% of simvastatin yield with a space-time yield of 4.61 g
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40 L⁻¹ h⁻¹ and specific productivity of 17 mg_{product} x mg_{enzyme}⁻¹ L⁻¹. This flow-biocatalysis system
41
42 improves some green chemistry metrics such as the reaction mass efficiency (RME) and the atom
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44 economy when compared to previous studies of simvastatin manufacturing.
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INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, the high demand for active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) like the cholesterol lowering drug simvastatin (SVA)^{1,2} encourages the development of novel technologies that shorten the time-to-market of pharmaceuticals. In this context, flow chemistry emerges as one of the most useful approaches to speed APIs discovery and manufacturing.³⁻⁵ Besides, biocatalysis is bursting into the API manufacturing model due to the excellent properties of enzymes as catalysts to advance toward more sustainable processes. In the last decade, chemical engineers have bridged biocatalysis and flow chemistry to intensify the production of pharmaceuticals.^{6,7} From the successful cooperation of these two disciplines, flow-biocatalysis is born to enhance the efficiency, sustainability, and safety of chemical manufacturing. All these reasons entail flow biocatalysis as a key enabling technology in green and sustainable chemistry. However, the integration of enzymes into flow reactors undergoes some limitations such as solubility, lability, and/or substrate inhibition that are inherent to the biological nature of the biocatalysts and must be tackled if a biochemical continuous process wants to be implemented.

One of the most adopted solutions to implement enzymes into flow-reactors is their immobilization on solid materials which enables their separation from the products and often enhances the stability and the reusability of the immobilized biocatalysts.⁸⁻¹⁰ In fact, a packed-bed reactor (PBR) formed by a column packed with an immobilized enzyme is one of the most widely used configurations in flow-biocatalysis.¹¹⁻¹³ Furthermore, enzymes can also be directly attached to the walls of microreactors, to the porous surface of thin films forming the membrane reactors, and to the inner surface of porous monoliths as part of the monolithic reactors.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ In all these cases, the enzymes can be considered heterogeneous biocatalysts where the catalytic sites are in a different phase (solid) than the reactants. Hence, the retention of enzyme activity and stability upon

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3 the immobilization process is not trivial as the enzymes bound to solid surfaces may undergo
4 negative structural distortions and suffer from mass transport restrictions of the reactants. When
5 the immobilization strategy is well designed and the resulting heterogeneous biocatalyst
6 profoundly characterized, one can maximize the activity/stability balance, giving rise to efficient
7 heterogeneous biocatalysts that can be continuously operated in a flow-reactor.¹⁸⁻²²

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16 Acyl transferases have been successfully applied in flow during the last decade for the
17 manufacturing of fragrances, flavors, and pharmaceuticals.²³ Remarkably, an acyl transferase from
18 *Mycobacterium smegmatis* has been immobilized on agarose porous microparticles functionalized
19 with aldehydes and packed into a PBR for the continuous synthesis of melatonin and other
20 tryptamine derivatives with an extraordinary space-time yield in an unprecedented short retention
21 time.²⁴ This example demonstrates that enzymatic processes can be intensified in flow up to
22 reaching the productivity and operational stability demanded by the industrial sector. In particular,
23 the intensification of acyl transferase driven processes is quite challenging as these enzymes
24 catalyze the transacylation reaction of different esters using different nucleophiles (alcohols,
25 amines, and thiols) through a kinetically controlled synthesis where synthetic and hydrolytic
26 activities compete.^{25, 26}

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42 An especially interesting case is the biosynthesis of SVA catalyzed *in vitro* by an
43 engineered acyl transferase LovD9 from *Aspergillus terreus* using α -dimethylbutyryl-S-
44 methylmercaptopropionate (DMB-SMMP) as acyl donor and yeast-fermented Monocolin J acid
45 (MJA) as acyl acceptor.²⁷ Unfortunately, this enzyme-driven acylation step suffers from substrate
46 inhibition by MJA and two unwanted side reactions underlying the mechanism of LovD9: the
47 hydrolysis of the acyl-enzyme complex ultimately converting DMB-SMMP into 2,2-
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dimethylbutanoic acid (thioesterase activity) and the hydrolysis of the final product back to MJA (esterase activity) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Mechanism of Simvastatin acid (SVA) synthesis and its side-reactions. DMB-SMMP: α-dimethylbutyryl-S-methyl-mercaptopropionate; DMB: dimethylbutyric acid; MJA: Monacolin J acid; SVA: Simvastatin acid. MJA inhibits the formation of the acyl-enzyme complex. The acyl-enzyme complex can be hydrolyzed by water (thioesterase activity), producing the dead-end product DMB. The product (SVA) can be hydrolyzed by the esterase activity of the enzyme to MJA and DMB (dead-end product).

In recent work,² we dissected the kinetically controlled synthesis of SVA catalyzed by LovD and created a new minimalist variant with only 14 mutations (LovD-BuCh2) and similar activity and stability properties as the *in vitro* evolved LovD9 (featuring 29 mutations);²⁸ the most efficient acetyl transferase variant ever reported for SVA biosynthesis. Despite having an excellent enzyme to catalyze such industrially relevant synthesis, this reaction has never been intensified

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3 through enzyme immobilization and engineering of a continuous process. In this work, we have
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5 optimized the immobilization of LovD-BuCh2 variant by testing different carriers and
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7 immobilization chemistries. The resulting heterogeneous biocatalysts were profoundly
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9 characterized at both structural and functional levels to find the optimal immobilization protocol
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11 that maximizes the activity/stability balance of the immobilized enzymes. This optimization and
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13 characterization voyage have enabled us to fabricate a heterogeneous biocatalyst (LovD-
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15 BuCh2@EziG1) that was successfully integrated into a PBR for the continuous synthesis of SVA.
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17 Tuning the flow conditions and substrate concentrations allowed us to reach 100% yield of SVA
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19 and minimize product hydrolysis that was limiting the SVA yield under steady-state conditions.
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25 **EXPERIMENTAL SECTION**

26 **Materials**

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31 Substrates Monacolin J acid (MJA) and α -dimethylbutyryl-S-methyl-mercaptopropionate
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33 (DMB-SMMP) were kindly donated by Prof. Yi Tang laboratory (UCLA, USA). Simvastatin
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35 hydroxyl acid ammonium salt 98% was purchased from Toronto Research Chemicals (Toronto,
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37 Canada). 2,2'-Dithiodipyridine 100%, Amicon Ultra-0.5 centrifugal filter units (10 kDa), NaBH₄,
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39 CoCl₂, iminodiacetic acid (IDA), rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RhB) and fluorescein
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41 isothiocyanate (FITC) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St.Louis, IL, USA). Agarose
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43 microbeads 4BCL (AG, particle size 50-150 μ m, pore size 50 nm) with (30 μ mol of Co²⁺ g support
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45 ⁻¹) (AG-Co²⁺) and without cobalt chelates were purchased from Agarose Bead Technologies
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47 (Madrid, Spain). Porous glass microbeads EziG1 (particle size 75-125 μ m, pore size 50 nm, 10
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49 μ mol Fe³⁺ g support ⁻¹) were kindly donated by EnginZyme (Stockholm, Sweden). His-tagged
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51 LovD-BuCh2 variant (**Table S1**) was overexpressed in *E. coli* BL21 strain as previously described
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(see Supporting Methods)². Only when LovD-BuCh2 was labelled with fluorophores, we used a pure enzyme solution which was purified through immobilized metal-affinity chromatography using AG-Co²⁺ for 1 h at 4 °C (see supporting information).^{2,29}.

Functionalization of agarose microbeads with epoxide groups and cobalt chelates (AG-Co²⁺/E)

1 g of agarose 4BCL was diluted in 1.6 mL of acetone and 44 mL of water containing 0.12 M of NaBH₄ and 0.1 M of NaOH at 4 °C. 11 mL of (±)-epichlorohydrin (≥ 99% purity) were added very slowly at the same temperature to avoid epoxide hydrolysis. The mixture was incubated for 16 h at room temperature with mild stirring. Finally, the suspension was filtered and washed with 10 mL of water. Then, 1 g of epoxy-agarose was modified by adding 0.5 M of iminodiacetic acid (IDA) in water at pH 11 and stirring at room temperature for 1 h with mild agitation. The suspension was filtered and washed with 10 mL of water. Under these conditions, the activation degree is 20.2 μmol g⁻¹ of IDA and 18.5 μmol g⁻¹ of epoxides according to the titration of remaining diols before and after functionalizing the epoxy-agarose with IDA. For quantification, the remaining diols in the agarose carriers were stoichiometrically oxidized with periodate, and the remaining periodate in solution was determined by the colorimetric oxidation of KI in basic media (water saturated with HCO₃⁻). 1 g of IDA-epoxy-agarose was additionally modified by adding 10 mL of a CoCl₂ solution (30 mg mL⁻¹ in water) and incubated for 1 h at 25 °C with mild stirring. Finally, the suspension was filtered, washed with 10 mL of water, and stored at 4 °C.

Enzymatic spectrophotometric assay

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3 Enzyme assay to determine the activity of both free and immobilized enzymes was
4 performed in 96-well plates for 30 min at 37 °C using 3 mM MJA, 2 mM DMB-SMMP and 2 mM
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6 2,2'- dithiodipyridine (2-DTDP) in 50 mM HEPES 10 mM MgCl₂ (pH 8) and 10% dimethyl
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8 sulfoxide (DMSO). The thiol formed (methyl mercaptopropionic acid, MMP) after the
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10 enzymatically driven thiolysis of DMB-SMMP spontaneously reacts with 2-DTDP, generating 2-
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12 thiopyridone that absorbs at 343 nm with an absorption coefficient of 7600 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (**Scheme**
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14 **S1**).³⁰ 1 unit of enzyme is defined as the amount of enzyme needed to produce one micromole of
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16 MMP per minute under the assay conditions.
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22 **Immobilization and one-step purification of LovD-BuCh2 on different carriers**

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26 5 mL of the clear crude extract containing His-tagged LovD-BuCh2 was diluted with 50
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28 mM HEPES at pH 8 until reaching 0.11 mg mL⁻¹ LovD-BuCh2 (enzyme concentration was
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30 estimated by SDS-PAGE, see supporting information). This enzyme solution was then incubated
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32 with 0.5 g of AG-Co²⁺, AG-Co²⁺/E and EziG1. A similar procedure was followed for the
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34 immobilization of the fluorophore-labelled pure enzyme. Upon the immobilization on AG-Co²⁺/E,
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36 the immobilized sample was incubated for 24 h at room temperature and pH 8. Next, the beads
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38 were filtered and incubated with 1 M glycine solution in phosphate buffer 50 mM at 4 °C and pH
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40 8 for 2 h, to react with and remove the remaining epoxide groups, thus avoiding unspecific covalent
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42 interactions during enzyme storage and operational time. Then, the beads were washed with 10
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44 mL of 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, vacuum dried, and stored at 4 °C for further use.³¹ A
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46 fraction of the immobilized enzyme was eluted with 250 mM imidazole and 50 mM HEPES at pH
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48 8 to assess further assays with both soluble and immobilized enzymes. Immobilization yield for
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50 each carrier was quantitatively assessed through sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel
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52 electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) using bovine serum albumin (BSA) as titration protein curve (**Figure**
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3 **S1)** under reducing conditions, and through the Bradford protein assay,³² calculating the difference
4 of protein concentration between the supernatant before and after contacting it with the carriers.
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6 The immobilization parameters were determined as described in supporting information.
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10 **Microscopy and biophysical characterization of LovD-BuCh2 on different carriers**

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14 The protein distribution of the enzyme across the surface of the different carriers was
15 determined by Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy (CLSM) (see supporting information). To
16 that aim the pure enzyme (see supporting information for purification details) was first labelled
17 with a fluorophore (Rhodamine B or fluorescein). For more details, see supporting information.
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19 Moreover, the enzyme spatial distribution was also studied by Raman spectroscopic microscopy
20 using the unlabeled enzyme (see supporting information).
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29 Structural rearrangements and mobility of the free and immobilized protein were analyzed
30 by intrinsic protein fluorescence and protein fluorescence anisotropy of the immobilized enzymes
31 (see supporting information). Finally, the immobilized and free enzymes were thermally
32 inactivated at different temperatures. For further experimental details, see supporting information.
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39 **Operational stability of LovD-BuCh2 immobilized on AG-Co²⁺/E and EziG1 in batch**

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41 Batch reaction time courses were measured for free LovD-BuCh2, LovD-BuCh2@AG-
42 Co²⁺/E, and LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 at 3 mM MJA, 2mM DMB-SMMP in 50 mM HEPES and 10%
43 dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at pH 8 (reaction mixture). Reactions were initiated in a 1.5 mL
44 column by mixing either 65 mg of LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E (1.06 mg g⁻¹support) or 203 mg of
45 LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 (0.34 mg g⁻¹support) with 600 μ L of the reaction mixture. The reaction was
46 incubated a 25 °C and samples were withdrawn at 1, 2, 4, 8, and 24 h by filtering the reaction
47 mixture in order to separate the immobilized enzyme from the reaction crude. For the reusability
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3 experiment, we considered 24 h reaction cycles at 25° C under the conditions described above.
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5 After each reaction cycle, the immobilized enzymes were separated, washed with HEPES 50 mM,
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7 MgCl₂ 10 mM at pH 8, and placed back into the column for a consecutive 24 h reaction cycle.
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9 Samples were analyzed by Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC) (Waters 2690)
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11 equipped with a PDA detector using an ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 1.7 μm (2.1 x 50 mm)
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13 Waters column coupled to a LCT XE time-of-flight mass spectrometry detector with electrospray
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15 ionization source (ESI). Analytes were eluted with an isocratic mobile phase composed of 52%
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17 (v/v) of acetonitrile in water (0.1% (v/v) formic acid) for 15 min at a flow rate of 0.3 mL min⁻¹.
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20 21 **Continuous flow processing for simvastatin synthesis and hydrolysis with LovD-BuCh2** 22 23 **immobilized in EziG1**

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26 1 g of LovD-BuCh2 immobilized in EziG1 (0.34 mg g⁻¹ support) was packed in a 1.5 cm³
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28 column for flow experiments. Flow reactions were performed at 25 °C flushing 1 mM MJA, 2 mM
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30 DMB-SMMP in 50 mM HEPES (pH 8), and 10% DMSO at different flow rates (10, 20, 50, 100,
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32 and 200 μL min⁻¹) using a syringe pump 11-PLUS, Harvard apparatus (MA, USA). Collected
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34 samples at the outlet of the column were analyzed by UPLC/MS using the same method described
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36 above. Other substrate ratios were also tested for the continuous flow reactor: 3 mM MJA / 2 mM
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38 DMB-SMMP and 1 mM MJA / 2 mM DMB-SMMP, at both 20 and 100 μL min⁻¹. SVA
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40 hydrolysis was monitored by passing a solution of 2 mM SVA at flow rates of 10 μL min⁻¹ and
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42 100 μL min⁻¹. Different parameters such as residence time (τ), space-time yield (STY), specific
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44 productivity (SP), and enzyme total turnover number (TTN) were calculated as described in
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46 supporting information. Finally, the sustainability metrics of the system were assessed as described
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48 in supporting information.
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preparation and characterization of different LovD-BuCh2 heterogeneous biocatalysts

We tested two different porous carriers and three immobilization chemistries for the immobilization of LovD-BuCh2. We first selected two carriers; porous agarose microbeads (AG) functionalized with iminodiacetic cobalt-chelates (AG-Co²⁺) and porous glass particles functionalized with Fe³⁺-catechol complexes (EziG1). These two commercial carriers allow the site-directed but reversible immobilization of His-tagged enzymes (**Figure 1a,b**). In parallel, we functionalized plain agarose porous microbeads with two different reactive groups: Co²⁺-chelates and epoxides (AG-Co²⁺/E), which allow a two-step immobilization/rigidification process.³¹ In this concurrent immobilization process, the His-tagged enzyme is first approached to the carrier surface through a rapid affinity-based interaction driven by Co²⁺-chelates, and then covalent bonds are formed through the nucleophilic attack of some amino acids (i.e deprotonated Lys or Cys) in the enzyme surface to the epoxide groups of the carrier surface (**Figure 1c**). To promote such irreversible attachment, we incubated the immobilized enzymes on AG-Co²⁺/E for 24 h at pH 8 and then blocked the remaining epoxy groups with glycine to abolish the reactivity of carrier surface upon the immobilization protocol.

Figure 1. Chemical functionalization of porous carriers for different immobilization strategies. **(a)** Immobilization on agarose microbeads activated with cobalt-chelates (AG-Co²⁺). **(b)** Immobilization on porous glass beads functionalized with iron-catechol chelates (EziG1). **(c)** Immobilization on agarose microbeads activated with cobalt-chelates and epoxides (AG-Co²⁺/E).

A crude extract of LovD-BuCh2 in *E. coli* was incubated with each carrier. 100 and 95% of the offered LovD-BuCh2 was immobilized on AG-Co²⁺ and AG-Co²⁺/E carriers, respectively, achieving protein loads of 1.11 and 1.06 mg g⁻¹. In contrast, EziG1 was only able to immobilize 31 % of the offered LovD-BuCh2, which meant a protein load of 0.34 mg g⁻¹ (**Table 1**). Such lower immobilization yield might be explained by the unspecific interaction of non-tagged proteins of the crude extract and the lower density of the affinity metal-complexes in the surface of EziG1 (10 μmol Fe³⁺ g support⁻¹) compared to the surfaces of AG-Co²⁺ (30 μmol Co²⁺ g support⁻¹) and AG-Co²⁺/E (18.5 μmol Co²⁺ g support⁻¹). SDS-PAGE analysis confirms that the His-tagged enzyme remains in the supernatant upon the immobilization on EziG1, while AG-Co²⁺ and AG-Co²⁺/E carriers binds the His-tagged enzyme quantitatively as no band is detected in the immobilization supernatant (**Figure S1**). This phenomenon could be mostly explained by the more specific coordination of the His-tag to Co²⁺ compared with Fe³⁺.^{33, 34} Moreover, when LovD-BuCh2 immobilized on EziG1 was incubated at 100 °C with β-mercaptoethanol, the enzyme was

not leaked from the surface. According to the aminated polymer layer that coat the controlled-pore glass surface of EziG1 to anchor the catechol groups,³⁵ we suggest that this carrier can form additional electrostatic interactions with the enzyme that do not occur in agarose-based materials, providing a stronger binding under denaturing conditions. On the other hand, we observed that in both carrier and eluted fractions, 100% and 50% of the enzyme was eluted from AG-Co²⁺ and AG-Co²⁺/E, respectively, when compared to their corresponding offered crude extracts (**Figure S1**). In the case of AG-Co²⁺/E, we suggest that around half of the immobilized enzymes correctly established irreversible (covalent) bonds with the carrier. Yet the irreversible immobilization of all bound enzymes was not possible because the post-immobilization incubation occurred at pH 8; conditions that may not be alkaline enough to favor the interaction between the exposed nucleophilic residues (i.e Lys and Tyr) of all enzyme subunits and the epoxide of the carrier.³¹

Table 1. Immobilization parameters of LovD-BuCh2 in different carriers. Ψ : Protein immobilization yield; RA: recovered activity (activity measured upon the immobilization protocol); iSA: immobilized specific activity. rRA: the relative recovered activity of the immobilized enzymes regarding the specific activity of the free enzyme (0.41 U mg⁻¹). The physicochemical features of the carriers are described in Materials and Methods

Material	Support	Metal density ($\mu\text{mol} \times \text{g}^{-1}$)	Functional group	Ψ (protein) (%)	Load ($\text{mg} \text{g}^{-1}$ support)	RA ($\text{U} \text{g}^{-1}$ support)	iSA ($\text{U} \text{mg}^{-1}$)	rRA (%)
Agarose	AG-Co ²⁺	30	IDA-Co ²⁺	100	1.11	0.316	0.13	68.3
	AG-Co ²⁺ /E	18.5	IDA-Co ²⁺ /Epoxide	95.0	1.06	0.100	0.09	21.9
Glass	EziG1	10	Catechol-Fe ³⁺	30.8	0.34	0.114	0.34	82.9

The enzyme recovered activity per mass of carrier (RA) and the immobilized specific activity (iSA) significantly varied depending on the immobilization strategy and the carrier utilized. LovD-BuCh2 immobilized on AG-Co²⁺ (LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺) presented a RA of 0.316 U g⁻¹ of

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3 support and an iSA of 0.28 U mg^{-1} , considerably higher than for LovD-BuCh2 immobilized on
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5 AG-Co²⁺/E (LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E) (RA = 0.1 U g^{-1} of support; iSA = 0.09 U mg^{-1}). Due to
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7 the irreversibility of the covalent bonds formed between scattered residues of the protein and the
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9 epoxides in AG-Co²⁺/E, conformational changes in the protein structure may occur. Such
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11 structural distortions may explain the loss of specific activity of these heterogeneous biocatalysts
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13 when it is compared to the free enzyme (rRA = 21.9%). The lack of these covalent bonds in LovD-
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15 BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺ is translated into a weaker binding but also results in a less pronounced activity
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17 loss (rRA = 68.3%). In contrast, LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 showed a lower RA than LovD-
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19 BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺ (0.114 U g^{-1} of support), but the highest iSA (0.34 U mg^{-1}), which indicated
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21 that less enzyme was immobilized in the carrier, but the immobilized enzyme preserves more
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23 activity (rRA = 82.9%) than using the other two carriers.
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30 31 **Spatial distribution of LovD-BuCh2 in different carriers**

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33 The spatial distribution of the enzyme across the surface of porous carriers is a crucial
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35 parameter that affects the recovered activity of enzymes upon their immobilization.³⁶ To
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37 understand how LovD-BuCh2 is spatially organized through the porous surface of the three
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39 carriers herein tested, we chemically labeled the enzyme with the fluorophore Rhodamine B
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41 isothiocyanate (RhB). The three immobilization preparations using the RhB-labelled enzyme were
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43 analyzed by confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) (**Figure 2a-c**). RhB-LovD-BuCh2 was
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45 mainly localized in the outer regions of agarose-based materials (AG-Co²⁺ and AG-Co²⁺/E),
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47 similar to previous results obtained with His-tagged proteins immobilized on similar carriers. It is
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49 known that His-tag driven immobilizations are extremely fast and avoid the infiltration of enzymes
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51 towards inner particle regions. Consequently, the averaged infiltration distance calculated from the
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53 radial profile (**Figure S2**) of single particles (n = 20) was $6.54 \mu\text{m}$ and $3.29 \mu\text{m}$ for AG-Co²⁺ and
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3 AG-Co²⁺/E, respectively. (**Figure 2d**). 3D profiles (**Figure S3**) confirmed that the fluorescence in
4 LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺ was mostly detected on the surface of the particle, while this
5 fluorescence intensity was accumulated in even more external layers in the case of LovD-
6 BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E. When the empty carriers were analyzed by CLSM as negative controls, we
7 detected no fluorescence intensity within the particles (**Figure S3**), indicating that the fluorescence
8 of the immobilized samples corresponds to the enzyme location at the particle surface. We suggest
9 that the epoxide might have a contribution to the immobilization process accelerating the
10 immobilization rate and favoring the concentration of the enzyme in even more outer particle
11 regions. In contrast, RhB-LovD-BuCh2 colonized deeper regions of EziG1 resulting in a higher
12 protein infiltration distance (24.42 μm) (**Figure 2d**). Additional electrostatic interactions between
13 the enzyme and the EziG carrier might contribute to localize the enzyme in inner regions of the
14 porous carrier surface as observed for other enzymes.^{37, 38} Additionally, the larger infiltration
15 within the material is translated into a lower enzyme density per μm^3 of the carrier, thus reducing
16 the protein molecular packing, which could explain the superior rRA of LovD-BuCh2@EziG1
17 (**Table 1**).

Figure 2. (a-c) 40X magnification confocal microscope fluorescent images (20X in the right corner, red field) of LovD-BuCh2 labeled with Rhodamine isothiocyanate (RhB) and immobilized onto cobalt-activated agarose microbeads (AG-Co²⁺) (a), AG-Co²⁺ functionalized with epoxide groups (AG-Co²⁺/E) (b), and porous glass functionalized with Fe³⁺-catechol complexes (EziG1) (c). Infiltration distance values were calculated from fluorescence profiles of 20 single beads of similar size (see Figure S2) (d).

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3 To validate the distribution results obtained with fluorescence microscopy and to study the
4 enzyme/carrier interactions, we applied Raman microscopy and spectroscopy as reported for other
5 immobilized enzymes.³⁹⁻⁴³ To this aim, we acquired Raman maps of LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 and
6 applied True Component Analysis (TCA) to spatially and chemically resolve the different
7 chemical species within the Raman hyperspectral imaging data.⁴⁴ Analyzing the averaged spectra
8 and Raman maps of free and immobilized LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 by TCA, we identified the protein
9 Raman spectrum as one of the components in both free and immobilized enzyme (**Figure 3a**).
10 From this spectra, we identified a peak at 1447 cm^{-1} corresponding to the deformation of C-H
11 bonds of the protein (δ -CH) and the typical 1656 cm^{-1} peak assigned to the amide I region of
12 proteins.⁴⁰ TCA generates a component map that shows how the same protein Raman spectrum
13 shown in **Figure 3a** is located at the outer surface of the particles (**Figure 3b**). Looking closer to
14 the Raman spectrum (range $1200\text{-}1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$) (**Figure 3c**), we observed an increase in the signal
15 ratio between 1275 cm^{-1} and amide I peak when the N-3 atom of the imidazole ring binds to the
16 metal. On the other hand, the C4=C5 bond signal of the imidazole ring experiences a shift from
17 1600 cm^{-1} when it is free to 1580 cm^{-1} when it is bound to the metal. These spectroscopic signatures
18 agree with previous studies that report how histidine coordination to divalent metals can be
19 detected in the Raman spectrum.⁴⁵ Therefore, the Raman spectrum of the immobilized LovD-
20 BuCh2@EziG1 revealed that the enzyme is mainly located at the outer surface of the carrier in
21 agreement with the spatial distribution elicited by CLSM for the same sample (**Figure 2c**).
22 Furthermore, the differences found between the Raman spectra of the free and immobilized
23 enzyme suggest that some conformational changes occur in the protein upon the immobilization.
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Figure 3. (a) Averaged Raman spectra of free LovD-BuCh2 and LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 (100-3800 cm⁻¹ range). (b) LovD-BuCh2 immobilized on EziG1. Top: bright-field images, and bottom: Raman 2-D map obtained with True Component Analysis (TCA) of the Raman spectrum of the immobilized enzyme (blue line in panel a). (c) Zoom in of panel (a) to better visualize the spectral differences of the averaged Raman spectra of free LovD-BuCh2 (red) and LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 (blue) in the range from 1200 to 1750 cm⁻¹.

Thermal stability analysis

The thermal stability of enzymes is a key parameter for industrial processes in biocatalysis to guarantee the biocatalyst operability under drastic conditions and long times. It is well

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3 established that the rigidification of the enzyme backbone as a consequence of its binding to solid
4 carriers upgrades its resistance against inactivating agents. However, this immobilization-
5 mediated stabilization is generally linked with the decrease of the immobilized enzyme specific
6 activity (iSA).^{46, 47}
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12 To assess the stability of the three heterogeneous biocatalysts described in the previous
13 section, we incubated them at different temperatures for 1 h. **Figure 4a** reveals that LovD-
14 BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E and LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 retained more than 80% of their activity after
15 incubation at temperatures up to 40 °C, whereas LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺ and the free enzyme
16 retained only 50% of their initial activity upon 1 h incubation under the same temperature. Under
17 thermal incubation, we suggest that the free enzyme may experience protein aggregation or
18 conformation changes due to undesired protein interactions that alter their optimal secondary and
19 tertiary structure.⁴⁸ As expected from the mesophilic origin of this enzyme, all the soluble and
20 heterogeneous biocatalysts were almost fully inactivated upon incubation at 50 °C.
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33 Hence, we set 40 °C as the inactivation temperature to determine the thermal deactivation
34 kinetics and the half-life time ($t_{1/2}$) of the different heterogeneous biocatalysts. **Figure 4b** confirms
35 that the soluble enzyme was the most unstable preparation with a $t_{1/2} = 27.6$ minutes and an
36 inactivation constant $k_i = 1.497$, whereas LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺, LovD-BuCh2@EziG1, and
37 LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E keep more than 50% activity for more than 50 minutes with $k_i = 0.744$,
38 0.374 and 0.286, respectively (**Table S2**). These results indicate that the site-directed and
39 multivalent irreversible immobilization of LovD-BuCh2 on AG-Co²⁺/E enhances the enzyme
40 stability by a factor of 4, a similar stabilization factor to that achieved with the EziG1 carrier where
41 the enzyme was attached only through reversible interactions. The surface properties and the
42 functionalization of EziG1 carriers may promote additional non-covalent (electrostatic)
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interactions with the enzymes compared to the AG-Co²⁺ which only binds the enzyme through the His-tag. Therefore, the stabilization of LovD-BuCh2 in both EziG1 and AG-Co²⁺/E may be related to the multivalent binding (of different nature) between the enzyme and the surfaces of these carriers that would protect the immobilized enzymes against thermal inactivation. A similar trend was observed for the inactivation of these immobilized and free biocatalysts in DMSO; the solvent typically used to dissolve the acyl donor (DMB-SMMP) herein used for the acetylation reaction catalyzed by LovD-BuCh2 (Figure S4).

Figure 4. (a) Thermal inactivation of free and immobilized LovD-BuCh2 on different carriers at different temperatures for 1 h. The residual activity (%) was calculated based on the initial activity at 25 °C of each biocatalyst. (b) Inactivation time courses of LovD-BuCh2 immobilized on different carriers and its free counterpart incubated at 40 °C. All the activity assays to calculate the residual activity upon thermal incubation were performed with 3 mM MJA, and 2 mM DMB-SMMP.

Mobility and conformational studies of immobilized LovD-BuCh2

To better understand the molecular origin of the enzyme stabilization promoted by immobilization, biophysical techniques were employed to elucidate the structural rearrangements of the protein when immobilized on different carriers before and after thermal inactivation. Protein aromatic residues show intrinsic fluorescence that can be detected upon excitation at 280 nm and provide information about the protein folding/conformation states.^{49, 50} Therefore, structural changes in the protein when it is immobilized on a carrier or subjected to thermal shock can be detected via changes in its fluorescence spectrum. **Figure 5a** and **Figure S5** show a slight hypsochromic shift of the maximum emission wavelength (λ_{max}) from 335 nm to 330 nm when LovD-BuCh2 was immobilized in all the carriers and incubated at 25 °C compared to the free enzyme, unveiling a reduced solvent exposure of the aromatic residues upon immobilization process that suggests conformational changes in the enzyme when interacting with the carriers. The presence of those new conformations may explain the lower specific activity of the immobilized enzymes compared to their free counterpart. When the free and immobilized biocatalysts were incubated at 40 °C for 4 hours, the free enzyme exhibited a 50 nm bathochromic shift in λ_{max} because thermal unfolding induces a higher solvent exposure of the aromatic residues. The extent of that shift was significantly lower in the immobilized preparations: LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺ underwent a 5 nm red-shift in λ_{max} , while LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E and LovD-BuCh2-EziG1 maintained their λ_{max} upon incubation at 40 °C. Thus, when the enzyme is immobilized, the thermal shock impacts the protein folding less than when it is in solution. Another relevant observation is that besides the alleged rigidification provided by covalent binding in LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E that explains protein stabilization, EziG1-enzyme interactions also seemed to provide a more protected protein towards thermal shock. This fact agreed with the

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3 results obtained from thermal deactivation assays at 40 °C (**Figure 4. b**), which revealed that
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5 EziG1 affinity immobilization improves enzyme thermostability when compared to AG-Co²⁺.
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8 Besides conformational changes in tertiary structure, the reduction in mobility undergone
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10 by the enzymes after the immobilization process can also be assessed by determining their
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12 rotational tumbling by measuring the anisotropy of fluorophores conjugated to the protein
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14 structure. To that aim, we labeled LovD-BuCh2 with fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) and
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16 immobilized it on the three carriers above described. The protein fluorescence anisotropy of the
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18 labeled and immobilized enzymes was measured as described elsewhere⁵¹ (see **Experimental**
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20 **section**). The anisotropy of the immobilized enzymes was higher than that of the free ones in all
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22 cases, demonstrating that the immobilization process consistently reduced enzyme rotational
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24 tumbling, an indication of enzyme rigidification upon immobilization (**Figure 5b, Table S3**).
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26 LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺ exhibited an anisotropy two times higher than the free enzyme, whereas
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28 the enzyme anisotropy in LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 and LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E was 2.45 and
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30 2.94 times higher than in the free enzyme, respectively. When the relative anisotropy was plotted
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32 as a function of the thermal half-life at 40 °C, we found a linear positive correlation between those
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34 two parameters, supporting the idea that thermostability is enhanced by reducing the protein
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36 mobility when anchored to a solid surface.^{52,53} Irreversible and multipoint covalent immobilization
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38 promoted by AG-Co²⁺/E explains the higher compactness and the lower mobility of the
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40 immobilized enzymes according to Trp fluorescence and anisotropy studies, entailing the high
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42 stability of this biocatalyst. This correlation between the valency of the attachment and the protein
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44 deformation and its increasing effect on protein stability under denaturing conditions has already
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46 been reported for other immobilized proteins.^{54,55}
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Figure 5. (a) λ_{\max} of each biocatalyst after incubation at 25 °C and 40 °C for 4 h. (b) Normalized anisotropy as a function of the half-life time at 40 °C. The anisotropy of free LovD-BuCh2 was set to a reference value of 1.

Operational stability of LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 and LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E

In addition to thermal stability, operational stability is fundamental to assessing the potential of any heterogeneous biocatalysts. Herein, the two most thermostable heterogeneous biocatalysts LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E and LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 were exploited for the batch synthesis of SVA (**Figure 6a**). As expected from the immobilization parameters, immobilized enzymes produced SVA slower than the free enzyme. The yields and production rates were determined by UPLC-MS (**Figure S6**).

As observed in **Figure 6a**, the free enzyme reached 100% yield of SVA production in 8 h and was the fastest biocatalyst with a specific productivity (SP) of 0.58 mg_{SVA} mg_{enzyme}⁻¹ h⁻¹ after 8 h of reaction. In contrast, LovD-BuCh2-EziG1 and LovD-BuCh2-AG-Co²⁺/E exhibited SP of

0.20 and 0.07 mg SVA mg enzyme⁻¹ h⁻¹ after 8 h, and SVA yields of 75% and 50% after 24 h, respectively. The rate of SVA production was significantly slower using the enzyme irreversibly immobilized on AG-Co²⁺/E, in accordance with the low specific activity of this immobilized enzyme (**Table 1**). Interestingly, we observed a 15% reduction of the product yield after 8 h using the free enzyme as a biocatalyst, which suggests that the free enzyme hydrolyzes the accumulated product. Although we did not observe any transient product yield decay when using the heterogeneous biocatalysts, we cannot discard the existence of hydrolytic activity in those biotransformations as the time courses never reached a plateau.

Finally, the two heterogeneous biocatalysts herein tested were recycled in consecutive 24 h cycles (**Figure 6. b**). As a result, both LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E and LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 exhibited a considerably high operational stability. While the initial product yield achieved with LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 diminished from 75% to 50 % after 8 operational cycles, the lower SVA yield obtained with LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E after the first cycle (50%) remained constant during the same 8 cycles. Therefore, the heterogeneous biocatalyst with the highest thermal stability also exhibits the highest operational stability although its productivity was the lowest. Covalent immobilization in epoxide, glyoxyl, or glutaraldehyde- activated supports has already proven successful to stabilize protein structure, ensuring its reusability in several cycles of operation.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ However, LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 demonstrated that covalent attachment is not always necessary to obtain a reusable biocatalyst, as other factors such as surface distribution or electrostatic interactions can also guarantee high productivity for long operation times. Therefore, the excellent operational stability and the higher productivity of LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 encouraged us to exploit it for the continuous synthesis of SVA in a PBR.

Figure 6. (a) Batch reaction time courses for free LovD-BuCh₂, LovD-BuCh₂@AG-Co²⁺/E, and LovD-BuCh₂@EziG1 using 3 mM Monacolin J acid (MJA) and 2 mM α -dimethylbutyryl-S-methyl-mercaptopropionate (DMB-SMMP). (b) 24 h batch cycles under the same reaction conditions.

Continuous synthesis of SVA with a LovD-BuCh₂@EziG1 packed-flow reactor

To set a continuous synthesis of SVA to have better control of the reaction outcome, we packed a bed of 1 g of 0.34 mg g⁻¹ LovD-BuCh₂@EziG1 in a 1.5 cm³ column and tested the reaction with 1 mM MJA and 2 mM DMB-SMMP at different flow rates. **Figure 7a** shows that the higher the flow rate, the higher the SVA yield (reaching the maximum yield at 100 μ L min⁻¹). This is a counter-intuitive fact because high flow rates normally decrease the residence times lowering the product yields. However, this reasoning is only valid for those systems where a single reaction takes place at a time, which is not the case of LovD-BuCh₂ that catalyzes the kinetically controlled synthesis of SVA where two unwanted side hydrolytic reactions (product and acyl donor hydrolysis) occur simultaneously to the target synthetic reaction. We hypothesize that the

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3 unwanted hydrolysis of SVA emerges with long residence times, explaining the lower SVA yields
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5 at low flow rates. Similar effects were reported for continuous flow kinetically controlled synthesis
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7 of oligosaccharides catalyzed by a glycosidase.⁵⁹ Looking at the product yields, we suggest that
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9 the lower the flow rate, the higher the product hydrolysis and the lower the SVA synthesis within
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11 the 10 to 100 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ flow rate range. However, at a 200 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ flow rate, the residence times
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13 of MJA and DMB-SMMP were too short to allow their maximal diffusion towards the active sites
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15 of the immobilized enzymes, resulting in a too low synthetic rate to further maximize the SVA
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17 yield. Despite achieving a lower SVA titer, the SP of the reactor is doubled from 100 to 200 μL
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19 min^{-1} flow rate, which means that the heterogeneous biocatalyst maximizes its productivity at 200
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21 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ flow rate although it does not reach the quantitative conversion into the product. Hence,
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23 100 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ seems to be the optimum flow rate to maximize both SVA yield and enzyme
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25 productivity at once.
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31 To confirm the effect of flow rate on the synthesis/hydrolysis trade-off, we operated the
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33 packed-bed reactor (PBR) with a 1 mM SVA solution at two different flow rates (10 and 100 μL
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35 min^{-1}) (**Figure S7**). Herein, we observed that low flow rates (10 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) led to the hydrolysis of
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37 56% SVA, while the synthetic reaction with MJA and the acyl donor only reached 23% SVA yield
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39 under the same PBR conditions (catalysts load, temperature, and substrate concentration). On the
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41 contrary, high flow rates (100 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) allowed 26% SVA hydrolysis and 65% SVA synthetic
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43 yield under the same conditions. These results suggest that the SVA synthesis is faster than its
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45 hydrolysis, thus the product is formed in short times under low flow rates, but it is then hydrolyzed
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47 if the residence time is too high, resulting in a steady-state SVA yield lower than expected. Hence,
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49 the comparison of MJA and SVA yields under the same PBR conditions proved that hydrolysis of
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51 the product can be reduced and the yield of SVA increased at higher flow rates. Therefore, by
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3 controlling the flow rate we can control the kinetic regimes of the kinetically controlled synthetic
4 process to maximize the steady-state product yield.
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8 With this information at hand, we set up a continuous flow process (CFP-1) operating at
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10 $100 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ (with a residence time of 12.5 min) flushing an excess of DMB-SMMP over MJA
11 (ratio 2:1). Under these conditions, the reactor achieved an SP of $10.74 \text{ mg SVA mg enzyme}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$
12 and a maximum yield of 70% after 2 h of operation (**Figure 7b**). CFP-1 maintained values close
13 to its maximum SVA yield for at least 6 reactor cycles of 30 minutes of operation. However,
14 quantitative MJA conversion to SVA (1 mM) was not achieved, probably because the competition
15 between synthetic and hydrolytic reactions was still significant.
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24 To maximize the SVA titer, we set a second continuous flow process (CFP-2) with a PBR
25 packing 370 mg of heterogeneous biocatalyst, using a flow rate of $20 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ (residence time of
26 23.1 minutes) and flushing 2 mM DMB-SMMP and 3 mM MJA (ratio 1:1.5). We hypothesized
27 that the excess of MJA over DMB-SMMP can shift the reaction towards SVA synthesis, mitigating
28 its hydrolysis. Our hypothesis was confirmed when a steady-state 70% of SVA yield was achieved
29 after 8 hours of steady-state operation (**Figure 7c**), with meant a noticeable improvement
30 compared to the 30% steady-state SVA yield achieved using a DMB-SMMP: MJA ratio of 2:1
31 under the same low flow rate conditions ($20 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$). Such high steady-state SVA yield (70%)
32 was maintained for 7 reactor cycles of 4 h each, demonstrating that LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 is also
33 operationally stable in continuous flow processes. However, quantitative SVA yield was not
34 achieved probably due to the hydrolytic capability of the immobilized biocatalyst, which was
35 boosted at higher residence times. After 36 hours of operation, the yield started to decay to 52%,
36 suggesting the partial inactivation of the immobilized enzyme. We suggest that the protein
37 inactivation caused by the continuous operation under the reaction conditions (i.e 10% DMSO)
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3 may rely on some structural distortions of the immobilized enzyme provoked by the organic
4 solvent (see **Figure S4**). However, we discarded the enzyme leaching as an inactivation cause as
5 we did not observe enzyme elution under the denaturing conditions of SDS-PAGE analysis
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10 **(Figure S1)**.

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15 To achieve the maximum yield overcoming the limitations of previous experiments, we set
16 a third continuous flow process (CFP-3) with a flow rate of $100 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ using 1 g of biocatalyst
17 (residence time of 12.5 min) and flushing 2 mM of DMB-SMMP and 3 mM of MJA (ratio 1:1.5).
18 These reactor conditions raised the SP to $16.95 \text{ mg SVA mg enzyme}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, achieving 100% of yield
19 after 40 minutes of operation (**Figure 7d**). This SP is 85 times higher than the one obtained in a
20 batch reactor under the same conditions. This optimization sequence is summarized in **Table S4**
21 and supports the hypothesis that both low flow rates and excess of acyl donor limit the final SVA
22 titer of the continuous flow process. Remarkably, the intensification of the process allows us to
23 reach an accumulated total turnover number (TTN) for LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 of almost 4×10^3 .
24 As the immobilized enzyme showed negligible inactivation, we foresee that CFP-3 can be operated
25 for more than 12 reactor cycles reaching even higher TTN. Although the CFP-3 is still far from
26 the titer demanded by an industrial application, the yield (100%), the STY ($4,61 \text{ g} \times \text{L}^{-1} \times \text{h}^{-1}$), and
27 the specific yield ($35 \text{ g SVA} \times \text{g enzyme}^{-1}$) fall close to the range of values demanded in manufacturing
28 of high-priced products such as SVA according to Meissner and Woodley.⁶⁰
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Figure 7. (a) Simvastatin acid (SVA) yield (%) and specific productivity (in $\text{mg SVA} \times \text{mg enzyme}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) in a packed-bed reactor loaded with LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 and operated at different flow rates (from 10 to 200 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$). The load of the reactor was 1 μM of immobilized enzyme and 1 mM MJA and 2 mM dimethylbutyryl-*S*-methyl-mercaptopropionate (DMB-SMMP) mixture was flushed. (b) SVA yield (%) and accumulated total turnover number (TTN, in mol of SVA per mol of enzyme) of CFP-1 after consecutive 30 min reaction cycles with a flow rate of 100 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ (1 mM MJA and 2 mM DMB-SMMP). (c) SVA yield and TTN of CFP-2 after consecutive 4 h reaction cycles with a flow rate of 20 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ (3 mM MJA and 2 mM DMB-SMMP). (d) SVA yield and TTN of CFP-3 after consecutive 20 min reaction cycles with a flow rate of 100 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ (3 mM MJA and 2 mM DMB-SMMP).

Sustainability metrics

The excellent results obtained with both batch and flow operations in terms of activity, stability, and reusability led us to compare the sustainability of the systems herein presented, as well as fermentative and chemical processes for the synthesis of SVA previously described in the literature.^{1, 27} To do so, we calculated sustainability metrics for batch and continuous. **Figure 8a** reveals that CFP-3 displays an improvement in SVA yield and reaction mass efficiency (RME) when compared to free LovD-BuCh2 and batch LovD-BuCh2-EziG1. RME, atom economy (AE) and 1/stoichiometric factor (SF) are also higher for CFP-3 (using LovD-BuCh2@EziG1) than for the fermentative (Bond 2019) and the chemical (Askin 1991) production of SVA. Mass productivity is the only parameter for which the chemical process is still superior to our new heterogeneous biocatalysts operated in flow. In contrast, **Figure 8b** shows that the E-factor of both continuous cell-free and fermentative^{1, 27} processes to synthesize SVA is significantly higher than the chemical process reported by Askin et al.¹ due to the larger contribution of wastewater to such parameter. When the water contribution is subtracted from the E-factor, the dissected E-factor of the process becomes lower for both batch, and CFP-3, using LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 than the one calculated for the chemical synthesis (**Figure S8**).

Figure 8. Sustainability metrics of the enzymatic synthesis of simvastatin acid (SVA). **(a)** Sustainability parameters for SVA synthesis (this work, Askin 1991 and Bond 2019). AE: atom economy. SF: stoichiometric factor. MP: mass productivity. RME: reaction mass efficiency. **(b)** Dissected E factor considers the individual contribution of reagents, solvents, water, and catalyst.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have fabricated three heterogeneous biocatalysts based on the very active variant LovD-BuCh2 of the simvastatin synthase LovD previously developed by us. We immobilized this enzyme on three different solid porous carriers, AG-Co²⁺, AG-Co²⁺/E, and EziG1 to screen the best carrier as well as the best immobilization chemistry. First, we have observed that immobilization yields and recovered activity depended on both the carrier and the chemistry of immobilization in a similar trend to other immobilized enzymes. We have found that the activity and stability of the immobilized enzymes are linked to their spatial distribution across the surface of the carriers, their conformation upon the immobilization process, and their rotational tumbling

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3 once immobilized. Mobility and conformational studies together with the microscopic
4 characterization of the immobilized enzyme revealed its spatial distribution across the surface of
5 the carrier. After evaluating the activity and the stability of the three heterogeneous biocatalysts
6 herein described, we conclude that LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 presents the best activity/stability
7 balance for their use in cell-free SVA biosynthesis. This heterogeneous biocatalyst exhibited an
8 excellent operational stability which allowed us to implement it in a continuous SVA synthesis
9 that was ultimately intensified by optimizing the flow rate, as well as the concentration and ratio
10 of the substrates. Remarkably, this work illustrates the potential of immobilizing engineered
11 enzymes for the process development of biotransformations. Finally, we assessed the sustainability
12 of the process herein reported in comparison with fermentative and chemical SVA synthetic
13 processes. The sustainability metrics revealed an outstanding mass efficiency and atom economy
14 of the process when using LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 operated in continuous under the optimal
15 conditions. However, the extensive use of water in this biotransformation was the major limitation
16 to achieving an E factor lower than 1000. As far as we know, this work is the first demonstration
17 of a heterogeneous biocatalyst for the continuous biomanufacturing of SVA. Further research of
18 continuous operational conditions is required to minimize the hydrolytic side reaction, as well as
19 the development of a downstream process of simvastatin purification and crystallization coupled
20 to the continuous flow process. We are confident that the lessons learned in this work will be
21 highly useful to implement other biocatalytic kinetically controlled syntheses in flow.
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ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Supporting methods, control experiments, and additional data including SDS-PAGE analysis, UPLC-MS chromatograms, CLSM profiles and protein intrinsic fluorescence spectra that support the main results are provided in the supporting information.

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41 their fruitful discussion of the results related to the immobilization on EziG.
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SYNOPSIS. In this study, we have developed a new prototype of immobilized acyltransferase LovD-BuCh2 in a continuous packed-bed reactor for simvastatin manufacturing.

TOC:

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